

MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM – LEVEL 1 AND LEVEL 2 BIOMAGNETIC PAIRS SCANNING METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is a non-invasive therapeutic technique based on the dysfunction of two specific anatomical points that sustain distortions at the glandular and tissue level, intoxication and can sustain pathogenic microorganisms. Dysfunctions are generated from changes in homeostasis, leading to acidity excess in one point and alkalinity excess in the other, beyond the ideal limit where nature determines health. Thus, the objective of this study is to present a standard model of the physical examination of Biomagnetic Pairs (BMPs) used in MB, called Scanning, which can be performed in two ways: Level 1 and Level 2. The standardization of the physical examination is essential so that the biomagnetism therapists and researchers of the technique can apply the technique in a systematic way. The present study is a narrative literature review of publications by Isaac Goiz Durán. The description of the Level 1 (Biomagnetic Scanning) and Level 2 (Bioenergetic Scanning) scanning method are presented.

This study can perpetuate this original method and build scientific grounds for analysis of BMPs, their properties and characteristics, as well as support new research that evaluate the MB treatment tool in a systematic way.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Scanning; Scanning Level 1; Bioenergetic Scanning; Scanning Level 2; Medicinal Biomagnetism Scanning Protocol; Biomagnetic Pair

1. INTRODUCTION

Magnetism has been used since the 6th century B.C., when Thales of Miletus observed that certain stones, magnetites, had the property of attracting each other and attracting iron (RODRIGUEZ, 1998). From this discovery, many scientists were focused on the study of magnetism, such as Pierre Pelerin de Maricourt, Paracelsus, Galileo, Robert Norman, Hans Christian Oesterd, Carl Friedrich Gauss, Maximilian Hell, Franz Anton Mesmer, Michael Faraday, Maxwell and Ampere (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

In 1936, Albert Roy Davis (considered the father of contemporary biomagnetism) together with Walter Rawls, demonstrated the effects of the north and south poles of magnets on blood, nerve, bacteria and plant cells. Thus arises the approximation between biology and magnetism (BROERINGMAYER, 1991). These effects were observed in actual studies (LIMA *et al.*, 2023; MARTINI *et al.*, 2023; SANTOS, P. *et al.*, 2023; SANTOS, L. *et al.*, 2023; DAMYANOV *et al.*, 2019a; DAMYANOV *et al.*, 2019b; ALBULQUERQUE *et al.*, 2016; FRANK, 2017).

Davis and Rawls demonstrated that the biological activity of cells increased with the application of a magnetic field. The metallic elements and ions contained in the cell, when exposed to a north pole, decreased the biological effects and reduced its activity. When applied to unhealthy cells, it produced a relaxed condition similar to the body's defense mechanism. When exposed to the south pole, their effects were opposite (DAVIS and RAWLS, 1974; PHILPOTT, 2000).

In the 1980s, Richard Broeringmeyer stood out as authority on magnetic therapy, energy therapy and biomagnetism. He spent many years dedicated to verifying

the effects of magnetic energy effects on cells, organs and systems of the human body, leading him to form a partnership with the International Biomagnetic Academy where he worked with Davis and Rawls in their research. Later, Broeringmeyer published a report on Magnetic Research and Nutrition (BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

Broeringmeyer, as a NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) physician, discovered an energetic phenomenon linked to biomagnetic fields that revolutionized the way of detecting regions with bioelectric impairment in the human body, called Right Hemibody Shortening (RHD) or Magnet-Sympathetic-Foot Reflex (MSFR) (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; CASTEJÓN, 2015).

Broeringmeyer observed that astronauts arrived from space with asymmetry of the lower limbs, neurological disorders and weakened immune systems. This observation led to the conclusion that these were consequences of their distancing from the Earth's magnetic field, which activated the primitive defense system of the human body (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

Based on Broeringmeyer's studies, Isaac Goiz Durán developed the therapy called Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB). The technique allows to localize unbalanced biomagnetic poles generated inside the body that are sustained by vibrational and energetic resonance. The magnets are then applied with the same polarities as the imbalances found to treat these disorders. In 1988 Goiz Durán identified the first Biomagnetic Pair (BMP), Thymus/Rectum (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

1.1 Understanding the Right Hemibody Shortening (RHS) Phenomenon

Goiz Durán was a physiotherapist and later became a physician. He worked at the National Institute of Pulmonology, (former General Hospital) and in his practice as a physiotherapist, he observed patients with lower limb asymmetry (LLA) presenting severe lung diseases daily. Patients who responded well to treatment had reduced asymmetry, and in some cases, recovered the limbs symmetry after remission of the pulmonary disease, when this asymmetry did not result from a permanent bone deformity (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

After he studied medicine, the hospital became a reference in several specialties. During his residency, Goiz Durán treated neurological patients, chronic kidney disease patients and patients with various illnesses, in whom he also observed lower limb asymmetry. As the clinical condition improved, the lower limb symmetry returned, while, as the disease progressed, the asymmetry increased. He lacked understanding of the processes involved in such anatomical responses (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

Having a background in physiotherapy, acupuncture, phytotherapy and medicine, Goiz Durán observed and treated the individual with an integral approach, seeking in integrative practices, the support of complementary treatments to conventional medicine. This led him to participate in the seminar on magnetic therapies, taught by Richard Broeringmeyer in 1988. Goiz Durán observed and made a correlation between the biomagnetic, energetic and immunological processes involved in pathologies, understanding the phenomenon to be a kinesiological response to health or disease (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

Broeringmeyer's technique was based on identifying charges generated by ionic dysfunctions, H⁺ and OH⁻, or other free radicals. When there was an accumulation of ions in specific regions of the organism, biomagnetic poles were formed. Where there was an accumulation of positive charges, a south pole was formed and where negative charges accumulated, a biomagnetic north pole was formed (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996; BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

The treatment to undo this accumulation of charges was to apply the north pole (Negative, Black or Scanning Magnet) of a therapeutic magnet over the positive charges to attract such charges by the Static Magnetic Field (SMF) generated by the magnet. To undo the accumulation of negative charges, the south pole (Positive, Red or Impacting Magnet) was applied. There was still no understanding that these charges were maintained by bioelectromagnetic resonance (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996; BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

From the stimulus generated by the SMF of a magnet, a kinesiological reflex with the Right Hemibody Shortening (RHS) is observed: the kinesiological reflex of the right lower limb indicating the presence of an unbalanced point. This kinesiological reflex is produced by the involuntary contraction of a group of muscles that go from the spine to the proximal region of the femur, the iliopsoas muscle being the most important in the resulting retraction (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

1.2 The Discovery of the Thymus/Rectum Biomagnetic Pair – Biomagnetic Scanning Level 1 (L1)

In the same year that he participated in Broeringmeyer's seminar, Isaac Goiz Durán received a terminally ill patient diagnosed with Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS) in his practice. This person was released by the doctors of the Public Health Service of Mexico for HIV positive patients with no prospect of recovery, weighing approximately 40 kilos (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

The patient's wife asked Goiz Durán to carry out the consultation and treatment, since the terminally ill patient had been through every medical procedure that was available. Goiz Durán ensured that all medical arrangements had been tried before making the choice to perform the magnetic therapy learned from Broeringmeyer (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

During the physical examination of the patient who was lying on a stretcher, Goiz Durán identified the Right Hemibody Shortening of approximately 2 centimeters. Applying a north pole magnet on diverse anatomical areas, Goiz Durán started a screening, called Biomagnetic Scanning (Level 1). In each area where the magnet was applied, Goiz Durán observed the lower limbs, checking the symmetry/asymmetry. When applying the magnet (impacting) in the thymus region, he observed that the right leg had shortened even more, increasing the asymmetry. According to what he learned during the seminar, Goiz Durán should invert the polarity of the magnet, keeping its south pole on the thymus and scan other areas of his body with the north pole of another magnet (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

However, upon impacting the north pole, coincidentally, a lamp in Goiz Durán's office exploded. The patient, a mechanic by profession, commented that there had been a shock of charges, a short circuit. Upon hearing about "shock of charges," Goiz Durán realized that the human organism could also present electrical alterations. He kept the north polarity of the magnet in the Thymus, where the negative charges were, and started a new scan, however, with another magnet, now with a south polarity, aiming to identify the positive charge that resonated with the negative charges present in the Thymus (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; GOIZ DURÁN, 1996; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

During the scanning to search for the point in resonance, defined as the phenomenon that happens when a physical system receives energy through excitations of frequencies equal to one of its natural vibration frequencies (BOSSA, 2021), he approached the south pole of the magnet to the coccyx region and observed that the lower limbs were symmetrical. He kept the magnets impacted for a certain amount of time. Afterwards, he removed the south pole and observed a smaller asymmetry. He kept the magnet for a few more minutes and, finally, when he removed it, the limbs remained symmetrical, that is, the BMP had been depolarized. This balanced condition is called Normal Energy Level (NEL) and defines the bioenergetic limits where all cellular metabolic processes of human organisms are maintained and which body temperature variation cannot exceed one degree celsius (it must be between 36 to 37 °C) (BOSSA *et al.*, 2023). The bioenergetic alteration of NEL obeys the ALL-or-None Law, which refers to a phenomenon that needs to reach a certain condition in order to happen, as occurs in the action potential of cells. The NEL acts as a dielectric in the formation and stability of each BMP. There is another dielectric that allows homeostasis, an aspect that is not considered in biochemistry, but in bioenergetics (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA *et al.*, 2023).

Goiz Durán identified the point of south polarity with accumulation of H⁺ as being the Rectum, naming this first pair, that maintains biological terrain for HIV (in the Rectum), as "Thymus/Rectum". Later, he identified that in this pair, the HIV (in the Rectum with excess of H⁺) maintains resonance with the bacteria *Escherichia coli*, sustained by the biological terrain with accumulation of

negative charges, OH⁻ (in the Thymus). Thus, the Biomagnetic Pair was defined as the set of charges that identify a pathology and that is formed by two main charges of opposite polarity that are formed independently of the fundamental alteration of the pH of the organs that support it (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA *et al.*, 2023; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

A few days later, the patient returned to the office without showing symptoms of diarrhea, lack of appetite and vomiting. He had gained weight and reported to feel better in general. This patient became a regular follower of Goiz Durán. He returned to the Public Health Center where he was undergoing the previous treatment, disclosed Goiz Durán's treatment taking another 18 seropositive patients in different stages of the disease to undergo the magnetic Scanning procedure with Isaac Goiz Duran (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996).

Thus, Goiz Durán had his first patients whose treatments were the basis of his first book, entitled "El SIDA Es Curable" (AIDS is curable), that had its first edition on February 4, 1993.

1.3 The Creation of the "Pathogen Code"

From the physical examination with the magnet applied to the patient's body, called Biomagnetic Scanning, or Level 1 Scanning, used to identify the Thymus/Rectum Pair, Goiz Durán scanned other patients with different complaints. In this way, it was possible to identify a variety of other pairs that treated certain symptoms. He associated other pathogens with other pairs discovered later, originating what he called the "pathogen code", defining the bases of a new therapy, Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB), which originated the BMP Scanning protocol (CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023). The "pathogen code" is based on the distortion of two specific points for each pathogenic microorganism, glandular or tissue dysfunction. These are distorted by excess acidity or alkalinity beyond the limit of relative neutrality where nature conditions health (GOIZ DURÁN, 1996; FRANK, 2017; BOSSA, 2021). The technique uses medium intensity magnets above 1,000 Gauss as a diagnostic and treatment tool and normally

does not exceed 7,500 Gauss for safety reasons (MARYCZ *et al.*, 2018; ZHANG, 2017).

1.4 The Evolution of the Scanning – Bioenergetic Scanning Level 2 (L2)

In 1993, the MB was already used by Goiz Durán in his private practice. To reduce the patient's care time, his wife helped him by applying the magnet, while he observed the symmetry/asymmetry of the limbs (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

At first, Goiz Durán asked his assistant, a nursing technician, to position the magnet at a certain scanning point. Some time later, due to the practice and mechanical nature of the method, both had already automated their actions. At one point in one scanning, Goiz Durán observed asymmetry in the lower limbs even before the magnet was applied to the patient's skin. In this way, he accidentally inferred that the organism had responded to a mental and verbal stimulus in the same way that it responded to the magnet stimulus (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

He started to reproduce the procedure using only mental and verbal forces, confirming the same response with the magnet later and thus, he developed the Bioenergetic Scanning, called Level 2 (L2). This observation is based on a binary dialogue system that takes place through the therapist's mental intention and the patient's physiology, a phenomenon not yet scientifically proven, but reported in articles such as, "Reiki as a therapeutic form in health care : a narrative review of the literature" (FREITAG, 2015) and "Physiological effect of distant healing intention on initial bean growth" (OLIVEIRA, 2017).

This system allows the Biomagnetism Therapist to perform the Bioenergetic Diagnostic Scanning of the MB pairs. From the L2 Scanning, Goiz Durán started to identify new BMPs through questions to the patient's body which provided only one answer (binary system), to differentiate them from the pairs previously found with the magnet in the body, classifying them as L2 BMPs (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

Although this technique is not invasive, there are some contraindications for its application. Cases where the application of magnets are not indicated include regions of the body with batteries (pacemakers or electrical devices) and during the first trimester of pregnancy in abdomen region. Absolute contraindication occurs in the case of hemodynamically unstable patients (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

The technique has been replicated in free courses, which allows freedom of interpretation and applicability. This action hinders not only the standardization of the examination and treatment, but also the scientific investigation to obtain greater evidence of this therapeutic technique.

Thus, the objective of this work is to describe the methodology of the Biomagnetic (L1) and Bioenergetic (L2) scannings of BMPs, presenting a didactic form so that it can be used in a standardized way in studies and clinical practice.

2. METHODOLOGY

This work is a narrative literature review of the technique developed by Isaac Goiz Durán, including handout from his courses and his books and those of his immediate students, with searches carried out in the digital library of Par Magnético Institute (IPM), to describe the process of discovering BMPs, as well as the development of Scanning Level 1 (L1) and Level 2 (L2).

It has an exploratory character with the aim of establishing Durán's scanning protocol. This type of research aims to get closer to the reality of the object studied, in this case, the physical examination of Medicinal Biomagnetism (PRAÇA, 2015; SOUSA, OLIVEIRA, ALVES, 2021). Because it is the presentation of a developed technique, only the publications related to the technique were selected. To maintain the originality of the content, other authors who do not address the MB theme were excluded.

3. RESULTS

As a result of the methodological search, 8 books were selected, whose author is Isaac Goiz Durán, developer of the Medicinal Biomagnetism Technique (MB): "El

Par Biomagnético (The Biomagnetic Pair) (2008)", "El SIDA es curable (AIDS is curable) (1996)", "El Fenómeno Tumoral (The tumor phenomenon) (2003)", "El Código Patógeno (The pathogen code) (2010))", "Fisiopatología Bioenergética (Bioenergetic Physiopathology) (2014)", "Par Biomagnético, Biomagnetismo Médico Y Bioenergética, Experiencias de Curación (Biomagnetic Pair, Medical Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics, Healing Experiences – Volume I, Volume II) (2005)" and "Par Biomagnético hongos, virus, bacterias y parásitos (Biomagnetic Pair fungi, viruses, bacteria and parasites) (2010)". Other references used for this study include 7 books that address the topic of Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics and 28 articles published on Medicinal Biomagnetism and Integrative and Complementary Practices that support the theme of this article.

After the exploratory search and, to improve the didactic process, the results of the L1 and L2 scannings are presented in separate topics. In the practical application of MB, BMPs L1 and L2 can be identified both by Biomagnetic Scanning (L1) and by Bioenergetic Scanning (L2). At the end of the BMPs scanning, it is necessary to apply L2 due to the possibility of bioenergetic diagnosis which, due to its characteristic of binary communication, expands the energetic diagnostic possibilities for Tumor Phenomena (infiltrate, exudate, cyst, abscess, dysplasia, neoplasm, metastasis, necrosis and cancer); Vascular Phenomena (edema, hemorrhage, embolism, thrombosis, calcification, hematoma, spasms, clot, aneurysm, stroke); Other Phenomena (calcification, hypertrophy, hyperplasia, metaplasia, hypotrophy and fibrosis); Potential Spaces (spaces filled with liquids due to the presence of two viruses, which may lead to inflammation, edema and, subsequently, evolve into tumor phenomena); Types of Flow (blood, lymphatic, humoral, air, reticuloendothelial) (BOSSA, 2023; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

Still using Scanning L2, the possibility of identifying Psycho-Emotional Problems; Emotional problems; Sophrological (body integrity problems, where suffering is caused by major trauma); Hormonal (hormonal and glandular dysfunction); Lack of Organics and Inorganics (proteins, carbohydrates, lipids, vitamins, enzymes and trace elements); Intoxications and Poisoning (toxins); Spiritual and Malignancy Problems (problems that affect the psyche, stress and addictions);

Chakras (Energy Distribution Centers); Chromosomes (bioenergetic alterations of one of the 23 chromosome pairs) and; Need for Other Therapies (such as: allopathy, homeopathy, naturopathy, etc.). In the MB physical examination, the above related items plus the BMPs constitute the Complete Scanning (CS) (BOSSA, 2023; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

3.1 Biomagnetic Scanning – Level 1

Place the person in a supine position, as shown in Figure 1, placing the feet outside the stretcher, which should preferably be made of wood. Hold the feet by the heels, lift them and bring them together. Scanning can be performed with the patient wearing shoes or barefoot. If shoes are on, it is necessary that they are closed, tight, and do not come off easily from the foot (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; MACEDO *et al.*, 2023; HONDA *et al.*, 2023).

The patient should remain lying or sitting on a stretcher, in order to keep the lower limbs relaxed. Pillows can be used to support below the knees as well as other utensils that provide comfort to the patient. (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; GOIZ MARTINEZ, 2018)

Figure 1: Body Position on the stretcher

Caption: Photo of the demonstration of a Bioenergetic Scanning (L2) being carried out by Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán on a volunteer during one of his courses.

Source: www.DSalud.com

Before starting the scanning, the alignment of the lower limbs or even the upper limbs must be checked. If there is symmetry, as shown in Figures 2a and 2b, scanning can begin. If there is asymmetry, Figure 2c, the Goiz Pair, as shown in Figure 2d must be applied, with the south (positive) pole of the MB therapeutic magnet on the “Kidney” point on the same side of the shortened limb and the north (negative) pole of another magnet at the contralateral “Parietal” point. If the Goiz Pair corrects the asymmetry, it should be maintained until the end of the scanning (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; HONDA *et al.*, 2023).

If symmetry does not occur with this impaction, the asymmetry is considered structural. The pair of magnets is removed and a level mark is made with a ballpoint pen, or with some adhesive tape, which will be a reference for symmetry (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

Figure 2: Biomagnetic Diagnosis and Treatment – Right Hemibody Shortening as bioelectromagnetic dysfunction on the scanning point

**MAGNET (+) ON KIDNEY ON THE SAME SIDE AS THE SHORTENED LEG AND
MAGNET (-) ON CONTRALATERAL PARIETAL**

Caption: Demonstration of the symmetry and asymmetry of the lower limbs and demonstration of a level mark performed in bare feet. 2a: LL alignment, normal function or after dysfunction correction with BMP impaction; 2b: Level marking, in bare feet; 2c: Lower limb misalignment due to bioelectromagnetic or structural dysfunction; in the 2d image it is possible to verify the impaction of a Biomagnetic Pair, named Par Goiz. **Source:** The authors, adapted from Bossa (2021).

After leveling, either anatomically, with marking, or with BMP correction, the negative pole of a MB magnet is applied over a predetermined anatomical point (pineal, right eye, left eye, thyroid, coronary, cervical 3, ...). The predetermined points constitute the complete scanning protocol that was gathered in a single file (BOSSA, 2021), integrating all parts of the scanning lists distributed throughout the books published by Goiz Durán (CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

As each point is applied, the alignment of the lower limbs must be observed. While there is symmetry, the Biomagnetism therapist can proceed to the next scanning point. When identifying an asymmetry after applying the negative pole to any of the anatomical points, the magnet must be maintained in this location, secured with an adhesive tape or in another way that does not allow the magnet to move. Bilateral scanning points, such as right and left eye, right and left ear, right and left wrist, right and left patella, etc., without asymmetry occurring after

the impact of the negative pole on one side of the body, the other side should be impacted with the same negative pole and checked if asymmetry of the lower limbs will occur (HONDA *et al.*, 2023; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023; MACEDO *et al.*, 2023; DOS SANTOS *et al.*, 2023).

After asymmetry is observed through the Magnet-Sympathetic-Foot Reflex (MSFR) by the action of the negative pole on an anatomic region, the positive pole of another magnet is used to check the points of resonance (or impaction). In the scanning protocol, each scanning point can have one or more resonance points. If there is more than one resonance point, the proposed sequence of resonances must be verified and the magnet must be applied on the resonant point where feet are balanced. This characterizes the formation of a BMP (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018). The process is repeated following all the scanning points contained in the complete scanning protocol, always observing the alignment of the lower limbs after each application (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

The BMP treatment ends when the magnet with the positive pole facing the skin is removed and the unevenness is no longer observed on lower limbs because this BMP has already been depolarized. When removing the positive pole magnet, the corresponding negative pole can immediately be removed. The procedure should be repeated for all magnets applied with the positive pole. If unevenness of feet is still observed after removing the positive pole magnet, it must be placed back on the skin and remain for a few more minutes. The procedure must be repeated until there is no unevenness, always after the removal of the positive pole verification (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; HONDA *et al.*, 2023; MACEDO *et al.*, 2023).

After removing all impacted BMPs, the patient can be released and a new scanning can be performed in an average period of 8 days, until no more BMPs appear during the scanning (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; HONDA *et al.*, 2023; MACEDO *et al.*, 2023).

3.2 Bioenergetic Scanning – Level 2

The procedure to apply the Bioenergetic Scanning is the same as in the Biomagnetic Scanning. The patient's position on the stretcher, the relaxation of the limbs and their leveling. The differentiation between these scanings lies in the way of performing the MB diagnosis to identify the BMPs (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

To identify a dysfunctional scanning point, the Biomagnetism therapist uses the mental/verbal command, which can be just mental, pronouncing or mentalizing the name of the point to scan, for example, "Thymus" (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023). If there is no kinesiological response of RHS, the Biomagnetism therapist proceeds to pronouncing the names of the next points of the sequence in the complete scanning protocol one by one (GOIZ DURÁN, 2014; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

If there is a kinesiological response with shortening of the limb, the impaction points related (in resonance) to that scanning point are also called. In this case, the Thymus point has 8 possibilities of resonance, which may be more if we consider the bilateral anatomical regions, such as ovaries, testicles or parietal. The resonance in dysfunction can be identified when, after calling the possible resonant point, the lower limbs are aligned (BOSSA, 2023).

The presence of this pair identified by L2 must be confirmed by applying the magnets as described in L1. The L2 scanning should continue until all scanning points are mentalized/verbalized and all those with dysfunction are identified and impacted, as well as their resonances. These must always be confirmed with the application of magnets. The correction of the dysfunction can be confirmed mentally, when the Biomagnetism therapist asks whether the BMP depolarization has been completed. If so, there will be no RHS and the magnets can be removed. The depolarization can also be verified as described at the end of the L1 Scanning (BOSSA, 2023; GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

4. DISCUSSION

The effects of magnetic field has been studied by many scientists over the past decades. Davis and Rawls verified and demonstrated the alteration of the

biological activity of cells when submitted to the magnetic field (DAVIS and RAWLS, 1974). In parallel, physician and scientist Richard Broeringmeyer has also done research on this same effect on cells, organs and systems in the human body. Later, Broeringmeyer published a bulletin on magnetic research and nutrition. As his research continued, Richard Broeringmeyer noted the phenomenon of RHS. He also observed LL asymmetry present in cases of neurological disorders and weakness of the immune system of astronauts arriving from space, due to the effects of the absence of the earth's magnetic field and also the formation of pairs with bioelectrical dysfunctions located in anatomical points in the human body (BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

On the other hand, Dr. Enrique Castejón (2012) deepened his knowledge of microorganisms that were found in dysfunctional pairs formed in the human body, relating them to pathologies and symptoms and, through the use of the static magnetic field of magnets, managed to achieve the rebalancing of these pairs.

Another scientist who dedicated himself to the research of magnets application to the human body was Raymond Hilu, who, through blood tests verified in the cellular morphological microscopy system, found alterations in the red blood cells of people with diagnosed diseases (HILU, 2010). In a pilot study, Frank (2017) identified and treated pathogenic microorganisms in humans using magnets (typhoid fever caused by *Salmonella typhi* bacteria) and Cazella (2023) demonstrated the same association of BMPs with *Escherichia Coli* in the treatment of recurrent urinary tract infections. Another study showed evidence of how the static magnetic field influences cellular systems (ALBUQUERQUE, 2016).

Damyantov and collaborators (2021) successfully applied a technique for the treatment of cancer using IPT & BPT-MB (Insulin Potentiated Therapy & Biomagnetic Therapy with Magnetic Pairs – Medicinal Biomagnetism) combined in patients with various cancers and metastatic tumors after they did not respond to conventional medical treatments for their illnesses. Their study resulted in remission of the disease in different degrees, and in some

cases, to the complete remission of the tumors after the complementary intervention that became the main alternative. A case study demonstrated remission of prostatic adenocarcinoma for discrete chronic inflammation with the application of three sessions of BM (MARTINI *et al.*, 2023), while another work demonstrated remission in endometrial polyps (SANTOS, L. *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, the Medicinal Biomagnetism technique is already being used by more than 2500 doctors all over the world, in addition to an uncountable amount of Biomagnetism therapists.

With the development of MB, other techniques have been practiced along with the teachings of MB, which compromises the proof of results of this therapy in a clear way, in addition to the fact that there is no standardization of the method to allow the advance in scientific studies (ECCLES, 2005; MAYROVITZ *et al.*, 2021).

There are several *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies demonstrating the effect of magnetic fields on cells (ALBULQUERQUE *et al.*, 2016; FENG *et al.*, 2022; PITTLER; BROWN; ERNST, 2007; ECCLES *et al.*, 2005; COLBERT *et al.*, 2008; FAN *et al.*, 2021, LIMA *et al.*, 2023; CAZELLA *et al.*, 2023; MARTINI *et al.*, 2023; ARAÚJO; FERREIRA; BOSSA, 2023).

The kinesiological test, when used by Bioenergetics, gives the possibility of bioenergetic diagnosis. “From 1993 it was realized and proven that the mind can replace magnetic energy” (GOIZ DURÁN, 2014). Medical bioenergetics consists of using the mind to identify “The Biomagnetic Pair” (bioelectromagnetic and pH distortion that can support pathogens), which dialogues directly with the DNA”, that is, the DNA has polarity and, therefore, when impacting the magnet on the body, its magnetic field will interact with the DNA (GOIZ DURÁN, 2014).

It was understood that the mind can replace magnetic energy and this concept opens new horizons for biomedical research, as it allows to enter into subjective concepts of psychology, sophrology, as well as in human emotion and spirituality, to aim directly at the etiology of a problem (GOIZ DURÁN, 2003; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008). Therefore, it is essential that the protocol method be obeyed by

Biomagnetism therapists worldwide so that this technique can have its results evaluated to allow the study of the method (CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

5. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The L1 and L2 Scanning protocol of the Biomagnetic Pairs of Medicinal Biomagnetism are presented in this research, as taught by Dr. Goiz Durán, developer of this therapeutic system. The importance of this original study is due to the increase of the use of this knowledge that has been spreading and gaining more and more followers. As well as the growing number of users, there is also an increase in the number of schools that teach the method, however, sometimes mixing with elements from other techniques.

The use of different techniques for the same purpose can end up generating new procedures, making the practical systematization of this knowledge difficult, or even preventing the construction and consolidation of the scientific bases for the MB.

It is hoped that the content of the present study can serve to perpetuate the original MB Scanning Method left by Isaac Goiz Durán, as well as to give base for studies that evaluate BMPs, their properties and characteristics, and the possibility of treating them using the MB tool.

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